

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: BLEBOO****FIRST NAME: ANTHONY****PROGRAM CODE: DGEP****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: PERIOD SIX****INSTRUCTOR: PROF. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 2%

The author used the MSWord 2019 on Windows 10

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Explain what constitutes inadvertent Plagiarism.

- "The dishonest, but unintentional quote of a source and failing to cite it, or use of a source's words, citing it but failing to put them in quotation marks."**¹
- The intentional and dishonest quote of a source and refusal to cite it, or use of a source's words, citing it but refusing to put the words in quotation marks.
- The intentional and dishonest quote of a source and willful failure to cite it, or use of a source's words, citing it but willfully failing to put them in quotation marks.
- The unintentional but dishonest quote of a source and citing it wrongly, or the use of a source's words, citing it incorrectly but putting the words in quotation marks.

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research, Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Ninth Edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 80.

2. Briefly describe the notable differences between a reference list and a bibliography in the Chicago style.

- “The entry of the publication year in a reference list appears directly after the author’s name, whereas it is entered near the end for a bibliography.”²**
- The entry of author's last name appears directly after the publication year in the reference list, whereas it is entered near the end of a bibliography.
- The entries in the Bibliography and the associated footnotes differ, whereas the entries in the reference list and the in-text citation are the same.
- The first name is entered first in the Bibliography, whereas the last name is entered first in the reference list.

3. Is it prudent for a research student to admit to the supervisor that there are challenges with the data collected? Explain what strategy to be adopted to address the situation.

- It is not prudent; thus, the student need not communicate the data challenges to the supervisor to ensure his shortcomings are not exposed.
- It is prudent to communicate the data challenges to the supervisor, but be sure to share only data without challenges to the supervisor.
- It is not prudent to communicate the data challenges to the supervisor but address the situation through fabrication, falsification, or misrepresentation of data.
- It is prudent to communicate honestly with the supervisor and ensure “not to distort the image of the data to make a point.”³**

² Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research, Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*, 154.

³ Turabian, 100.

4. Explain the reasoning behind the advice that a researcher should write the introduction after the researcher has written a final draft of the dissertation.
- The “introduction includes, amongst others, the research purpose and its conduct.”⁴ It is best written after drafting the body of the dissertation.**
 - The introduction is an in-depth statement of the research purpose only and is most appropriately written after the dissertation draft.
 - The introduction overviews the research methodology only and is most appropriately written after the dissertation draft.
 - The introduction only provides an overview of data analysis and is most appropriately written after the dissertation draft.
5. Please explain why the title is the last thing written for a dissertation.
- Writing the title last enables the researcher to identify and use appropriate abbreviations, acronyms, and initials to explain the objective of the dissertation.
 - Writing the title last allows the researcher to build a general title without announcing the topic and communicating the conceptual framework.
 - “Writing the title last allows for it to be built out of earlier identified terms to announce the topic and communicate the conceptual framework.”⁵**
 - Writing the title last enables the researcher to be discreet about the dissertation until it is ready for submission. This prevents it from being plagiarized.

⁴ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*, Fourth Edition (California: Sage Publications Limited, 2019), 74..

⁵ Turabian, 155.

6. Name one key element of a complete dissertation and explain its importance in a complete dissertation.

- “The abstract summarizes the research process, and its information influences whether readers proceed to look at the total dissertation.”⁶**
- The problem statement describes the challenges the researcher identifies during the research and ensures the argumentation process is well-aligned with the topic.
- The set of research questions, which are always open-ended, helps the researcher in the process of collecting data.
- The set of research findings is always the result of the data analysis collected and helps in writing the dissertation's topic.

7. Briefly explain the differences between qualitative and quantitative research.

- "Qualitative research is traditionally descriptive, comparative, and investigates relationships. Quantitative research is traditionally narrative inquiry, discourse analysis, and phenomenology."⁷**
- Qualitative research is traditionally narrative and comparative. Quantitative research is traditionally subjective inquiry and discourse analysis.
- Qualitative research is traditionally narrative and causal/comparative. Quantitative research is descriptive inquiry, discourse analysis, and phenomenology.
- Qualitative research is traditionally narrative inquiry, discourse analysis, and phenomenology. Quantitative research is traditionally descriptive and comparative.

⁶ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 68.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, 137–41.

8. Briefly describe the appropriate data collection methods for qualitative and quantitative research.

- "Closed-ended question surveys, scales, and ranking order checklists are used for qualitative research. Observation, open-ended surveys, interviews, documents, and critical incident reviews are used for quantitative research."**⁸
- Open-ended questions surveys, scales, and ranking order checklists are used for qualitative research. Observation, close-ended surveys, interview documents, focus groups, and critical incident reviews are used for quantitative research.
- Only close-ended-question survey scales and ranking order checklists are used for qualitative research. Only interviews are used for quantitative research.
- Only observation and open-ended questions interviews are used for qualitative. Observation, surveys, and close-ended interviews are used for quantitative research.

9. Describe the Style guide in dissertation writing and why it is necessary.

- It ensures a unique approach to certain elements of writing style that must be consistent and that standards for a prescribed writing style are adhered to.
- It directs for specific dissertation structures to be adopted, making them unique and ensuring that the structures as prescribed are not necessarily adhered to.

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, 140–41.

- It is a means of “documenting the approach to certain elements of writing style that must be consistent and ensuring that standards are adhered to for common multiple authorship and readership interpretation.”⁹
- It ensures consistency with a supervisor's laid down approach and that the writer adheres to the standards for the prescribed writing style laid down by the supervisor.

10. Identify which statement below is not good for dissertation conclusion writing.

- Discuss the objective of the dissertation and whether the goals have been met.
- Identifying how it helped to understand the dissertation topic.
- Describing again all the points already stated in the body of the dissertation.**
“Conclusions must be concise and devoid of repetition and ambiguity.”¹⁰
- Reflecting on how the dissertation can inform any future dissertation of a reader.

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Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research, Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, and William T FitzGerald. Ninth ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

⁹ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1*, 41.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation*, 679.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.